

**Dehydrogenation of Methyl Alcohol and
Formaldehyde with Copper as Catalyst. A
Study of the Conditions of the Equilibrium
in the System : $\text{HCHO} \rightleftharpoons \text{CO} + \text{H}_2$**

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In a paper by Ghosh and Mali (this *Journal*, 1924, 1, 37) on the vapour pressure and chemical constant of formaldehyde it was suggested that the determination of chemical constant of this gas would be helpful in studying the conditions of equilibrium in the following reactions.

Sabatier and Mailhe found that with freshly reduced copper oxide at temperatures between 200° and 300°, "the thermal decomposition of methyl alcohol proceeds according to the equation (1) and the reaction is a *reversible one*. A 50% conversion is obtained with a 5% loss of decomposition products and 45% unchanged methyl alcohol" (Rideal and Taylor, *Catalysis in Theory and Practice*, p. 127).

That the decomposition of HCHO into CO and H₂ is a reversible one is suggested by Badische Patent

(Brit. Pat. 20486, 1913) and Dreyfus Patent (D.R.P. 108855, 1915) according to which formaldehyde is obtained by passing a mixture of carbon monoxide and hydrogen in the ratio of 2 to 1 at 100 atmospheres over catalytic materials at 300°–400°. Some unpublished investigations of Mr. K. P. Bose in this laboratory showed that equilibrium in the above reactions could not be attained by passing methyl alcohol vapour slowly over a space packed up with the catalyst below 300° as shown from the analysis of the outflow gases. The yield of formaldehyde and its decomposition into CO and H₂ was found to depend more on the nature of the catalyst than on the velocity of flow at a particular temperature. Thus with copper catalyst, obtained by reduction of freshly precipitated copper hydroxide, dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol began at 110° and at 170° it was about 40 per cent. Orange-red compact copper prepared by reduction of the dense oxide according to Sabatier's method gave only 10% yield of formaldehyde at 205°. Hence in these investigations a static method of attaining gaseous equilibrium was adopted. The arrangement was in many respects analogous to that devised by Rideal for measuring the hydrogenation of ethyl alcohol and acetone (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, [A] 99, 155).

EXPERIMENTAL.

The experimental arrangements will be clear from the diagram (Fig. 1). An electric tube-furnace, *F*, was maintained at a constant temperature for 10 to 15 hours at a stretch from a constant current battery of 220 volts. The range of temperature lay between 155° to 350°. The bulb of the reaction tube, *T*, was at the centre of the furnace and at the same temperature throughout its entire length. The tubes had capacities varying from

40—70 c.c. and were attached to a capillary tube with a side tube at one end which communicated through the stop-cock, *S*, with a mercury manometer, *M*. The bulb was filled with small pieces of pumice stone which were soaked with copper formate solution and ignited at 300° in a current of air (for details see Palmer, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, [A], 98, 13). The open end of the reaction tube was then drawn into a capillary, care being always taken that the length of the bulb of the reaction tube did not exceed two-thirds of the length of the furnace. The catalyst material was then reduced *in situ* by passing a current of pure hydrogen for six hours at a temperature of 250°. The stop-cock *S* was closed, methyl alcohol vapour from a twice distilled sample was passed into the reaction tube, the hydrogen inside was chased out and the ends sealed at constrictions previously made, first at *C*, then at *C'*. The furnace was maintained at the desired temperature and the pressure inside the tube at constant volume was noted by bringing the mercury level to a certain mark, *m*, above the stop-cock. The ends of the reaction tube projecting out of the furnace were wound round with manganin wire and maintained at about 100° by electrical heating. The vapours of alcohol were thus prevented from condensing in the capillary ends. The reaction was allowed to go on for twelve hours to ensure complete equilibrium which was indicated by constant pressure in the manometer. The capillary end *C* was then connected with rubber tubing to a carbon dioxide generator and *C''* to a Hempel gas burette. The capillary ends were broken inside the rubber tubing by applying pressure and the vapours inside the reaction tube were quickly chased out by carbon dioxide and collected over caustic soda solution in the gas burette. It is of course assumed that during the process of the collection of the gases the condition of the equilibrium

FIG. 1.

is not disturbed. The gas mixture contained hydrogen, methane and carbon monoxide and was analysed in the usual way. The aqueous solution was analysed for methyl alcohol and formaldehyde. The latter was estimated by Romijn's method. The total amount of formaldehyde and methyl alcohol was estimated by complete oxidation with 2*N* chromic acid and sulphuric acid and titrating back the chromic acid with potassium iodide solution (*Ber.*, 39, 325). Formaldehyde could also be indirectly estimated, for, it will be equivalent to the volume of hydrogen minus twice the volume of carbon monoxide in the mixture. Above 290° the formation of methane become appreciable and then it is not possible to determine the exact quantity of formaldehyde by the indirect method. We might assume, however, that at these temperatures, methane is formed according to the Armstrong-Hilditch reaction (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 103, 25),

and the amount of formaldehyde could thus be indirectly estimated. The amount of CO₂ in the gas mixture under equilibrium conditions could not be directly estimated but it could be estimated as equivalent to the amount of methane present. In fact the previous investigation of Bose showed that at these temperatures CO₂ and CH₄ were formed in equivalent quantities. The quantities of each of the following substances, *viz.*, CO, H₂, CH₄, CO₂, H.CHO and CH₃OH being known it is possible to calculate the partial pressure of each from the observed total pressure. It is obvious that the apparatus has to be dismantled after each experiment, and the catalyst has to be prepared anew. This is necessary in view of the well-known fact that the activity of the catalyst rapidly diminishes with time.

The values of equilibrium constants at 340° and 380° were not very reliable as the quantities of formaldehyde were small for direct estimation and the indirect estimation becomes somewhat uncertain because of the increasing quantities of methane being formed at higher temperatures. Beyond 345° the equilibrium could not be determined.

Experimental Results and Discussions

Tables I and II give respectively the observed equilibrium constants of the reactions (1) and (2).

$$K_{p(1)} = \frac{p_{\text{HCHO}} \times p_{\text{H}_2}}{p_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}}} \quad \text{and} \quad K_{p(2)} = \frac{p_{\text{CO}} \times p_{\text{H}_2}}{p_{\text{HCHO}}}$$

TABLE I.

T	K_p (obs.)	K_p (cal.)
155°C	.37	.39
205°C	.65	2.24

K_p (cal.) in column 3 of the Table I is obtained from the equation,

$$\log_{10} K_p = \frac{-10700}{4.571T} + 1.75 \log_{10} T - 3.75 \times 10^{-4} T + .8 \quad \dots (3)$$

Rideal gives the following theoretical equation for the decomposition of ethyl alcohol,

$$\log_{10} K_p = \frac{-10700}{4.571T} + 1.75 \log_{10} T - 3.75 \times 10^{-4} T + 2.2.$$

The heat of dissociation of methyl alcohol into formaldehyde and hydrogen cannot be fixed with certainty as the exact heat of formation of formaldehyde is not known. Rideal gives 10700 cal. as heat of dissociation of ethyl alcohol. The heat of dissociation of propyl alcohol is 10450 cal. (heat of formation of propyl alcohol being 65690 cal. and that of propionic aldehyde 55240 cal. Thomsen, *Thermo-Chemistry*). We are therefore, not very much wrong in fixing the heat of dissociation of methyl alcohol at the above figure. The chemical constant of hydrogen according to Nernst is 1.6. But Bakhuyzen in a recent paper (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1924, 111, 57) from a critical examination of the available data gives the value of the chemical constant as 1.1. For formaldehyde $C=3.5$, for methyl alcohol C might be taken to be 3.8, the same as propyl alcohol. Therefore $\Sigma \nu C=0.8$. The agreement between observed and calculated values of K_p at 155° is accidental. It is obvious that at 205° the dissociation of methyl alcohol corresponding to the conditions of equilibrium is not obtained. If, however, we take the chemical constant of methyl alcohol as 4.1 the same as that of ethyl alcohol, then $\Sigma \nu C=0.5$ and the calculated values of K_p at 155° and 200° are 0.195 and 1.12 respectively. The agreement with the observed values is no better.

TABLE II.

T°C.	155°	160°	205°	230°	250°	260°	295°	330°	340°
$K_p(\text{obs})$	0.082	0.086	0.13	0.27	0.48	0.56	0.94	1.6	2.20
$K_p(\text{cal.})$	0.028	0.032	0.13	0.32	0.40	0.50	0.98	1.9	2.31

$K_p(\text{cal.})$ in Table II is obtained from the equation,

$$\log_{10} K_p = \frac{-11800}{4.571T} + 1.75 \log_{10} T - 0.001T + 0.3 \quad \dots \text{(ii)}$$

The agreement is fairly good throughout. The difference between the heats of combustion of methyl alcohol and of carbon monoxide and 2H_2 , is 22550 calories. If the heat of dissociation of methyl alcohol into formaldehyde and hydrogen is fixed as 10700 cals. the heat of dissociation of formaldehyde into carbon monoxide and hydrogen comes out to be 11800 cals.

The Chemical Constant of Carbon Monoxide.

Nernst gives 3.5 as the chemical constant of carbon monoxide. Jellinek (*Physikalische Chemie der Gasreaktionen*, p. 466) gives 2.6 as the chemical constant of carbon monoxide. The chemical constant of nitrogen is 2.6 and in view of the fact that the physical properties of carbon monoxide and nitrogen are very similar as has been emphasised by Lewis and Langmuir, it appears that the value 2.6 for carbon monoxide is the probable one. Further according to Nernst the chemical constant of a gas is given by the empirical equation, $C=0.14\frac{\lambda}{T_0}$, where λ =molecular latent heat of vaporisation, T_0 =boiling point in absolute temp. at one atmosphere. From Landolt and Börnstein's *Tables*, 1923, we get $\lambda=1414$ cal. and $T_0=-190^\circ$, whence $C=2.4$.

The water gas reaction,

has also been very thoroughly investigated by Hahn (*Z. physical. Chem.*, 44, 513) and Engels (*Z. f. Gas Beleuchtung*, 62, 483) whose results are in mutual agreement. Sackur has shown that for this reaction the equation,

$$\log K_p = \frac{-2200}{T} + 2.0$$

gives values in agreement with the experimental data (*Thermo-Chemistry and Thermo-Dynamics*, Eng. Trans.,

1917, p. 314). ΣvC for the above reaction is therefore 2.0. C for hydrogen is 1.1; for water 3.6; for carbon dioxide 3.2 (Nernst's data) and C for carbon monoxide is 2.7. It thus appears that 2.7 is the more probable value for carbon monoxide and ΣvC in the reaction,

is therefore equal to 0.3. This is the value that has been taken in equation (ii).

It is thus clear from this investigation that the equilibrium conditions for dehydrogenation of methyl alcohol cannot be exactly ascertained with copper prepared in the usual way as the catalyst. But the dehydrogenation of formaldehyde appears to be a reversible reaction and the variation of equilibrium constants with temperature can be fairly well expressed by an equation of the Nernst type.

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